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Date: 03/05/2024

DH-DD(2024)494

Documents distributed at the request of a Representative shall be under the sole responsibility of the said Representative, without prejudice to the legal or political position of the Committee of Ministers.

Meeting: 1501st meeting (June 2024) (DH)

Reply from the authorities (30/04/2024) following a communication from the applicant concerning the case of Besnik Cani v. Albania (Application No. 37474/20).

Information made available under Rule 9.5 of the Rules of the Committee of Ministers for the supervision of the execution of judgments and of the terms of friendly settlements.

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Les documents distribués à la demande d'un/e Représentant/e le sont sous la seule responsabilité dudit/de ladite Représentant/e, sans préjuger de la position juridique ou politique du Comité des Ministres.

Réunion : 1501^e réunion (juin 2024) (DH)

Réponse des autorités (30/04/2024) suite à une communication du requérant relative à l'affaire Besnik Cani c. Albanie (requête n° 37474/20) **[anglais uniquement]**

Informations mises à disposition en vertu de la Règle 9.5 des Règles du Comité des Ministres pour la surveillance de l'exécution des arrêts et des termes des règlements amiables.

REPUBLIKA E SHQIPËRIË
STATE ADVOCATURE
OFFICE OF GENERAL STATE ADVOCATE

No. 1278/3 Prot.

Tirana, on 28.4.2024

Ref: On the execution of the judgment of the European Court of Human Rights in the application no. 37474/20 "*Besnik Cani v. Albania*".

To: **Ms. DIMITRINA LILOVSKA**
Head of Division
Department for the Execution of Judgments of the ECHR
DGI - Directorate General of Human Rights and Rule of Law

Council of Europe- Strasbourg
67075 Cedex
France

Dear Mrs. Lilovska,

In relation to the letter from the applicant in the case no.37474/20 "*Besnik Cani v. Albania*" communicated to the Albanian Government on 7.3.2024, we would like to submit the following:

The Albanian Government has submitted on 12.9.2023, the Action Report on the individual and general measures implemented by the Albanian Government for the execution of the ECtHR judgment in the application no.37474/20 "*Besnik Cani v. Albania*".

As already stated in the Action Report, in relation to the execution of the individual measures, from official communication with the Special Appeal Chamber¹, it results that there is no registered request in the registry of the Special Appeal Chamber from the applicant for the reopening of the proceedings.

In addition, after the letter from the applicant, the State Advocate Office, by letter no 1278/1 dated 19.3.2024 has made a new request for information to the Special Appeal Chamber. The Special Appeal Chamber has informed the State Advocate Office that from the data in the SAC Registry,

¹ Letter of the SAC no 262/3 dated 19.7.2023

it results that there is no request for the reopening of the proceedings by the applicant Mr. Besnik Cani.

In this regard, we recall the findings of the Court in paragraph §150 of the judgment, that the request of the applicant to quash the SAC's decision of 27 February 2020 and order the Government to reinstate him immediately in his former office was refused by the Court based on its jurisdiction (see paragraph 139 of the judgment) and the nature of the violation that was found in respect of the applicant's vetting proceedings.

Therefore, as the Court has indicated, in paragraph 144-150 of the judgment, under application of Article 46 of the Convention, "given the circumstances of the present case and to the extent that that it might be possible under domestic law, the most appropriate form of redress for the violation of the applicant's right to a "tribunal established by law" under Article 6 § 1 of the Convention would be to reopen the proceedings, should the applicant request such reopening, and to re-examine the case in a manner that is keeping with all the requirements of Article 6 § 1 of the Convention". The Court has also indicated in the judgment that according to the domestic legislation on the vetting proceedings, the SAC would be the body with jurisdiction to consider such requests².

Based on the above considerations, the Albanian Government considers that it has fulfilled its obligations under article 46 of the Convention and requests to the Committee of Ministers to close its supervision, in respect of the case Besnik Cani v. Albania, application no. 37474/20.

Yours sincerely,

ODISE MOÇKA

STATE ADVOCATE GENERAL

² Moreover, the applicant was dismissed from office by the Special Appeal Chamber.